

FORMULA FACTORIZATION (Prime Number)

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$$p * q = n$$

$$\frac{n}{0,2875} = n1$$

$$n * \frac{808}{n1} = n2$$

$$\frac{n2}{n1} = n3$$

$$\frac{n2}{n} = n4$$

$$\frac{n3}{n4} = p \text{ or } q \text{ The most little of } p \text{ or } q$$

Example 1

$$43 * 29 = 1247$$

$$\frac{1247}{0,2875} = 4337,3$$

$$1247 * \frac{808}{4337} = 232,3209$$

$$\frac{23232}{4337} = 5,5356$$

$$\frac{23232}{1247} = 18,6$$

$$\frac{535}{18} = 29,7 = p \text{ or } q \text{ The most little of } p \text{ or } q$$

Example 2

$$3 * 10007 = 30021$$

$$\frac{30021}{0,2875} = 104420,8695$$

$$30021 * \frac{808}{104420} = 232,30193$$

$$\frac{2323019}{104420} = 22,24668779$$

$$\frac{2323019}{3001} = 77,379$$

$$\frac{22}{7} = 3,142 \text{ } p \text{ or } q \text{ The most little of } p \text{ or } q$$